

Inoculation method

1. Take several ufra-infested plants and tease them longitudinally. Cut into small pieces and soak in water overnight. Examine the extraction under a microscope and estimate *D. angustus* population per plant. Prepare an inoculum to ensure each seedling in the test receives 100 nematodes. Infested plants should be teased as before, cut into small pieces, and spread evenly over the plot in shallow standing water.

Postinoculation management

1. After inoculation, raise water level to the uppermost seedling node. Maintain this level for the first few weeks.
2. Once seedlings start to elongate, flood the tank to maintain water level at the uppermost node. This is necessary for 34 months after inoculation.

Observation and sampling

1. Inspect plants regularly for chlorotic discoloration of the leaf base, just below the collar. This discoloration is characteristic of ufra dur-

Rice variety classification.

Plant condition	Nematodes/tiller (av no.)	Infestation (%)	Reaction ^a
No disease symptom	None	Nil	HR
No disease symptom	1-100	1-20	R
Disease symptom visible	1-100	1-20	R
Disease symptom visible	101-300	21-60	I
Disease symptom visible	300+	61-100	S

^aHR = highly resistant. R = resistant, I = intermediate, S = susceptible.

ing vegetative phase and may be visible 3-4 weeks after inoculation. It more often is visible after 6-7 weeks, but 3-4 months is recommended to allow full development of chlorosis and spread of nematodes. At 3-4 months randomly sample at least 5 plants from each line.

Laboratory processing of plant samples

1. Dissect the individual plant to innermost tender leaf, cut into pieces about 5 mm long, place in a bijou bottle (or other small vial), add 2 ml tap water, loosely cover, and leave overnight.
2. Shake the container to thoroughly mix suspension. Examine 1 ml under a stereomicroscope, using a 1-ml Peters mounting slide to count nematodes. A few nematodes

should be examined by compound microscope (100×–400×) to ascertain the proportion of *D. angustus* in the sample.

3. Calculate total number of nematodes per tiller, average number of nematodes per tiller, and percentage of infestation of each variety or breeding line.

Scoring rice varieties

Classify the test varieties into the categories in the table.

Precautions

Some varieties may not show a consistent relation between the average number of nematodes per tiller and the observed percentage of infestation. Such varieties should be left as unclassified and considered for retesting. *h*

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Selection for rice cold tolerance using grain yields versus phenotypic acceptability

G. S. Chung, M. H. Heu, B. S. Vergara, J. D. Yea, G. Pateña, and R. M. Visperas, IRRI

In the rice cold tolerance nursery, selection is based on leaf color, panicle exsertion, growth duration, fertility, and phenotypic acceptability (PA). However, the ultimate measure of performance is grain yield and field performance. An observational yield trial for low temperature areas was started in 1980 at Chuncheon Experiment Station, Korea, to study PA and compare yields. One hundred entries were planted in 1980 and in 1981.

Many entries yielded high (see table) but some yielded low because of high sterility, caused partly by delayed heading.

Several lines of IR crosses yielded high indicating the improvement rice breeders have made on old varieties. In most crosses, Kn-1b-361 was important. IR9202 (IR2053-521-1-1/K116//Kn-1b-361) was promising. IR2053 was early and had good grain quality. K116, from India, and Kn-1b-361, from Indonesia, are cold tolerant.

Cold tolerance at panicle initiation and flowering stage must be improved for Chianan 2, Chianung 242, K-84, and Khonorollo. They are high yielding under moderate temperatures but showed low percentage of fertility in

Results of the 1980-81 observational yield trial for low temperature areas, Chuncheon, Korea.

Designation	Yield (t/ha)	PA
<i>1980</i>		
China 988	6.81	5
IR7167-33-2-3-3-1-3	6.45	3
IR9202-5-2-2	6.60	5
IR9202-6-1-1-2-2	6.51	3
IR9202-10-2-1-1-3	6.85	5
IR9202-10-2-1-5-1	6.30	5
IR15636-8-3	7.30	5
IR15889-32-1	7.89	7
Shoa-Nan-Tsan	6.45	5
SR3044-78-3	7.30	3
SR4079-4-2	6.30	9
Cheoulwon 21 (check)	5.51	5
<i>1981</i>		
SR5204-91-4-1	6.92	3
IR15924-265-3	6.69	6
IR9202-33-4-2-1	6.41	5
IR7167-33-2-3-3-1-3-1	6.40	3
IR20897-B-45	6.28	3
Suweon 235 (check)	3.77	3

Korea.

Most high yield varieties had a 3 to 5 PA score. PA is a poor measure of performance or yield ability. Many entries had poor PA but yielded high.

Low PA and grain yield correlation resulted because short stature is more

desirable in Korea, where high nitrogen levels are used. In 1981 PA was not correlated with visual plant characters — days to heading, panicle number per hill, and spikelets per panicle. It was correlated with plant height ($r = 0.59^{**}$), which is not correlated with grain yield.

PA is a location-specific measurement. PA scoring in the observational yield trial should be discontinued to increase efficiency and allow more entries to be tested. *h*

Pest management and control DISEASES

Improved method for obtaining viable counts of *Xanthomonas oryzae*

R. W. H. Parry and J. A. Callow, Plant Sciences Department, University of Leeds, LS2 9JT, UK; and E. R. Morris, Unilever Research, Colworth Laboratory, Sharnbrook, Bedford, MK44 1LQ, UK

Recovering colonies from single *Xanthomonas oryzae* cells is difficult. Recent experiments show improved recovery

Table 1. Components of three media for growth of *X. oryzae*.

Component	Qty (g/liter)		
	Dye's	WF-P	Goto's
(NH ₄) ₂ HPO ₄	1.00	—	—
K ₂ HPO ₄	2.00	—	—
KCl	2.00	—	—
Na ₂ HPO ₄ · 12H ₂ O	—	2.00	—
Ca(NO ₃) ₂ · 4H ₂ O	—	0.50	—
FeSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	—	0.50 ^a	—
MgSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	0.20	—	—
Na-glutamate	—	—	1.00
Yeast extract	1.00	—	—
Peptone	—	5.00	10.00
sucrose	10.00	20.00	10.00
Agar ^b			
Spread medium	17.00	17.00	17.00
Poured medium	4.00	4.00	4.00

^aAccording to S. H. Ou, "Rice diseases," p. 59.

^bOxoid No. 3.

results if *X. oryzae* is poured into a weak agar medium. Colonies in poured preparations are counted more easily because they spread more slowly than those from bacterial suspension on the surface of agar medium.

After 48 hours incubation at 28° C, up to 400 colonies can be resolved on a 9-cm petri dish. These remain suitable for counting for at least 60 hours. The poured method is faster than surface spreading, and contamination is reduced.

Spread and poured cultures from a decimal dilution series of *X. oryzae* PXO 71 were prepared on three commonly used media (Table 1). Preliminary experiments showed 0.4% wt/vol agar to be the most suitable concentration for viable counting.

Spread cultures were prepared by dispensing 0.1 cm³ of bacterial suspension onto the surface of lightly dried medium and spreading with a sterile glass rod. Poured cultures were prepared by placing 0.1 cm³ of suspension into a sterile petri dish, and adding 10-20 cm³ of medium, held molten at 38-40° C. The dish was swirled to ensure even inocu-

lum distribution.

Uniform colonies developed in the poured media. They were counted after 60 hours. Spread cultures were counted after 84 hours because growth was uneven and some colonies appeared later and grew more slowly than others (Table 2).

Live counts were higher for poured than spread preparations for all media. Goto's medium supported growth better than WF-P or Dye's medium. Dye's medium was unsuitable. Growth dependence on inoculum density was overcome only when samples were poured into weak Goto's medium. This, together with the high viable counts obtained (more than 50% total count) and the high degree of reproducibility between replications, suggests pour-plating in Goto's medium containing 0.4% agar is the best way of obtaining viable *X. oryzae* counts.

The method has been used successfully for quantitative recovery of several strains of *X. oryzae* from infected rice plants, and should be useful in genetic procedures requiring isolated mutant recovery. *h*

Table 2. Colonies of *X. oryzae* per 9-cm petri dish.^a

Dilution	Colonies ^b (no./9-cm petri dish)					
	Dye's		WF-P		Goto's	
	Pour	Spread	Pour	Spread	Pour	Spread
1	c	c	c	c	c	c
10 ⁻¹	c	0	c	c	c	c
10 ⁻²	c	0	c	c	c	c
10 ⁻³	c	0	c	c	c	c
10 ⁻⁴	c	0	c	c	c	c
10 ⁻⁵	1500 ^c	0	2000 ^c	1500 ^c	2000 ^c	1500 ^c
10 ⁻⁶	107.3 ± 11.1	0	212.7 ± 15.7	31.3 ± 16.8	223.0 ± 5.3	100.3 ± 20.0
10 ⁻⁷	3.0 ± 0.6	0	14.7 ± 2.4	0	21.7 ± 2.2	3.0 ± 1.5
10 ⁻⁸	0	0	1.3 ± 0.3	0	2.3 ± 0.9	0

^aMeans of triplicates ± standard errors are shown. Total bacterial count (viable and nonviable) estimated using counting chamber at 4.4 x 10⁹/cm³ original suspension. ^bc = confluent growth. ^cApproximate count.